

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

WP2 Mapping of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures: Interview guidelines

Disclaimer

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Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (IR) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

1. Introduction to the ALL-Ready WP2 mapping

Work package 2 aims to map and analyse research infrastructures, living labs and open innovation arrangements, along with policies and funding arrangements across Europe, that are linked to agroecology transition. This is with the ambition to gain an overview of the 'landscape' and understand enablers, barriers and incentives for innovation for agroecology transition, with specific attention to:

- The innovation systems that underpin agroecology systems, such as agroecology living labs and research
- The role of societal drivers, in particular funding arrangements and regulatory frameworks

The interview guide aims to provide input to the following WP 2 deliverables:

D.2.3 Report on drivers of agroecology transition

D.2.4 Overview of agroecology living labs and research infrastructures in Europe

D.2.5 Agroecology open Innovation: best cases across Europe

D.2.6 Towards a network of agroecology living labs

Methodology

The interview guide has been designed on the basis of the characterisations and definitions of what constitutes agroecological production system and agroecological living labs and research infrastructures, prepared in WP1 (c.f. ALL-READY Deliverable 1.1 and 1.2 in particular). Further, the requested information for the deliverables, along with resource availability, as well as the need to avoid respondent fatigue, have been key parameters in delimiting the scope of the inquiry.

Country Coverage: In total, 22 countries will be mapped, 5 of which will be mapped jointly with the AE4EU CSA. Please consult the 'List of NCP's' for reference.

The Respondents (or National Contact Points- NCPs): Are the main entry point for providing an overview of the national contexts. These are professionals such as case officers in ministries, researchers, and civil society. Most, but not all, will be proficient in English. They should be considered key informants, and as such, they are expected to have in-depth knowledge on the agricultural sector in their countries, yet represent different perspectives. Key informants enable the collection of information that we can use analytically, not information that that can be generalized statistically. To the extent possible, 3 NCPs, representing policymaking, research and practice have been identified (and have consented to be interviewed) for each of the 22 countries to be mapped.

The Interview Guide: The interview guide contains (1) a series of closed questions as well as (2) a series of in-depth open-ended questions. The closed questions allow for some degree of comparison across countries. The open questions allow for elaboration of responses to the closed questions and for additional reflections. Questions are organised thematically, with closed questions being followed by open ones.

Conducting the interviews: Interviewers will be sourced from the WP2 mapping team. They will each handle a portfolio of countries, proportional to the person-months commitment of their organisation, allocated with their specific qualifications in relation to specific countries in mind. Based on the list of National Contact Points (NCPs), the All-Ready researchers (interviewers) will send the interview guide to the respondents in advance. The inquiry itself, however, will be conducted as an actual interview, by phone. The varying professional backgrounds of the NCPs may mean that not all NCPs may be able to respond to all questions. The researchers will need to assess this on a case-to-case basis. In some cases, such as when the list of NCPs does not cover all categories for a country, or when responses are deemed inadequate, the researcher will apply snowballing techniques, with a view to identifying alternative respondents.

Preparation: Prior to the launch of the interviews, the researchers will receive training on interview techniques, definitions etc. Researchers will also carry out desktop studies identifying relevant country-specific policies, research infrastructures etc. This is in order to become familiar with national initiatives that are relevant, as a basis for making the most out of the interviews.

2. Key definitions and concepts

The interview guide contains concepts – sometimes ambiguous - that need to be well understood by both the researcher and the respondents. The training session for the researchers will serve to ensure that researchers are able to explain the following concepts in context to the respondents:

Agroecology Transition is usually thought of as entailing different stages (Hill 2014¹, Gliessman 2016², WP1, D1): Efficiency, which connotes better use of resources within existing farming modes; substitution, which connotes the replacement of technologies, and; redesign of the agroecosystem so that it functions on the basis of ecological processes. Contrary to the additive and incremental nature of efficiency and substitution measures, redesign addresses farming systems in a more transformative fashion and maximizes the coproduction of agricultural and environmental outcomes. The further along the efficiency-substitution-redesign gradient we climb, the higher the need for local agricultural knowledge and adaptation of known practices and in turn, cooperation and knowledge exchange (Pretty et al 2018³).

Living labs are defined by the European Network of Living labs (ENoLL) as “user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings”.

¹ Hill, S, 2014: Considerations for Enabling the Ecological Redesign of Organic and Conventional Agriculture: A Social Ecology and Psychosocial Perspective

²<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/21683565.2015.1130765>

The definition of agroecology living labs comes close to that of agroecosystem living labs, which have been defined in the draft proposal for an agroecology partnership as: “transdisciplinary approaches which involve farmers, scientists and other interested partners in the co-design, monitoring and evaluation of new and existing agricultural practices and technologies on working landscapes to improve their effectiveness and early adoption”. The changing of practices through co-creation and participative processes is considered conducive to the acceleration of agroecology transition (WP1, D.1).

Research infrastructures can be defined broadly as facilities that provide resources and services to conduct research and foster innovation. They include: major scientific equipment or sets of instruments; collections, archives or scientific data; computing systems and communication networks; any other research and innovation (R&I) infrastructure of a unique nature which is open to external users. In an agroecology transition perspective, the scope of these research infrastructures could include agriculture and agri-food redesign, sustainability assessment (impacts, ecosystem services, ecological, social and economic dimensions), vulnerability - adaptability - resilience assessment (emergent properties of agroecosystems) and dynamics of agroecology transition. Also, from a transition perspective, research infrastructures should have defined science-society-policy-users interphases. When providing central roles to users –such as farmers – these infrastructures may become open innovation arrangements that resemble living labs (see WP1, D.1)

Agroecological principles and elements: see <https://www.agroecology-europe.org/our-approach/principles/> as well as <http://www.fao.org/3/i9037en/i9037en.pdf>.

Agroecological practices: In agriculture, see <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13593-013-0180-7>

Stakeholders are typically farmers, farmer groups or associations that develop and implement agroecological practices, as well as farmers’ markets, Community Supported Agriculture (CSA) schemes and local products distribution channels, as well as other stakeholder initiatives that have a clear orientation towards agroecology (AE4EU).

3. Interview guide

The interview guide contains (1) closed questions as well as (2) a series of in-depth open-ended questions that allow for broadening the response to the closed questions and provide additional reflections.

The varying professional backgrounds (typically administration, research or civil society) of the NCPs mean that not all NCPs may be able to respond to all questions. The interviewer will need to assess this on a case-to-case basis. Following the interviews, the interviewer will complete a synthesis of the interviews, including the sources of information. Find the template for this in the next section.

Please complete one template for each NCP and before each interview please ensure that participants consent to the conditions of data collection as described in the "Information letter for collecting research data" found in appendix 1 of this guideline document.

Before commencing the interview, please explain the objective of the project, as outlined in section one, (introduction). Refer also to section 2, for explaining key concepts and definitions. Do not assume that the respondent knows these concepts.

3.1. Background information

(1) For the interviewer: Please record the following background information of the interview:

- a) Country: _____
- b) NPC interviewed (name): _____
- c) Organisation: _____

(2) Which of the following stakeholder categories do you belong to?

Public administration (e. g. government, municipality, funding body etc.)	
Researcher/Scientist	
NGO (e. g. farmers associations or other association, think-tank, etc.) (please specify) _____	

3.2. Defining Agroecology

Agroecology is a broad and complex concept. It is generally seen as a scientific field, a practice and a social movement. It is common to find different understandings and emphases within these three areas. This section explores these differences.

(3) On a scale from 1-5 how important are the different dimensions of agroecology in your country?

	(1) Very important	(2) Important	(3) Neutral	(4) Less important	(5) Unimportant	(x) I don't know
Practices – E.g. production practices that reduce input us, save resources, are characterised by diversity; agricultural systems and food systems where stakeholders (incl. farmers, consumers, authorities) are involved in decision-making, co-creating innovation etc.						
Science – E.g. research on applying ecological concepts and principles to optimise interactions between plants, animals, humans and the environment (agronomy + ecology), in agricultural systems and food systems)						
Social Movements – E.g. NGOs, cooperatives etc with focus on small-scale, family farming, food sovereignty, promoting values (incl. solidarity, rights, ecological justice) indigenous (diverse) seeds/breeds etc						

(4) Other reflections regarding the understanding of agroecology in your country?

3.3. The extent of agroecology-based practices within the country

(5) On a scale from 1 to 5 how commonly applied are the following agroecological principles and/or agroecology-based practices in your country?

	(1) Very common	(2) Common	(3) Neutral	(4) Somewhat common	(5) Unusual	(x) I don't know
Integrated Pest Management and Biological Control						
Conservation Tillage						
Mixed Cropping Systems						
Diversified Crop Rotation						
Cover Crops						
Fertiliser and Nutrient Management Efficiency/recycling						
Biodiversity Preservation						
Circularity in Biomass Utilisation						
Wetland Restoration with Paludiculture						
Sustainable Water Management						
Other						

(6) If other, please describe principles and/or practices and clarify extent of application:

(7) Are there regional differences with respect to the extent of application? Where and why is this the case?

(8) Other reflections regarding the extent of agroecology related principles and/or practices in your country?

3.4. Research and innovation systems in support of agroecology

Agroecology is considered as a key element in the green transition envisaged in key strategy documents, such as the European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork strategy etc.

(9) On a scale from 1 to 5 to which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding research and innovation systems in support of agroecology in your country?

	(1) To a high extent	(2) To some extent	(3) Neutral	(4) To a limited extent	(5) Not at all	(x) I don't know
Research infrastructures (research facilities) are sufficiently attuned to support agroecology transition						
Research programs have focus on agroecology transition						
Sufficient financial resources are allocated for research into agroecology-based practices						
Farmers needs in an agroecology transition are sufficiently reflected in current research activities						
Living labs and other forms of multi-actor involvement are used in agroecological research and innovation						
On farm experimentation is often applied in research activities						

(10) How can current research infrastructures be used to foster a transition towards agroecology-based practices?

(11) How can current research infrastructures and research programmes be improved to foster a transition towards agroecology-based practices?

(12) Other reflections regarding research infrastructures in your country?

3.5. Competencies for an agroecology transition

(13) On a scale from 1 to 5, how would you classify the state of the following elements in the context of agroecology in your country?

	(1) Very well developed	(2) Developed	(3) Neutral	(4) Somewhat developed	(5) Not developed at all	(x) I don't know
Education of farmers in agricultural colleges						
Technological infrastructure in the farming sector						
Knowledge networks among farmers						
Farm advisory service						
Resources available for training/retraining of farmers						
Farmer networks for knowledge sharing						
Other						

(14) If other, please specify:

(15) Other reflections regarding competencies for an agroecology transition?

3.6. Involvement of stakeholders in the agroecology transition

(16) On a scale from 1 to 5 to which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding stakeholder involvement with respect to agroecology related matters in your country?

	(1) To a high extent	(2) To some extent	(3) Neutral	(4) To a limited extent	(5) Not at all	(X) I don't know
Stakeholders are organised in associations that represent their interests						
Stakeholder associations possess a high level of technical expertise						
Stakeholders' views are taken into consideration in policymaking						
Stakeholders are well integrated in research programmes						
Stakeholder associations representing farmers have a strong interest in pursuing an agroecology transition						
Living labs and other open innovation arrangements are frequently used in to foster transition within your country						
Stakeholders are actively participating in multi-stakeholder living labs						

(17) How can the involvement of stakeholders for agroecology transition be improved in the country (in living labs and other open innovation arrangements)?

(18) Which stakeholder groups are primarily involved in the agroecology transition and are any stakeholder groups lacking?

(19) Other reflections regarding the involvement of stakeholder in the agroecology transition:

3.7. Policies in Support of Agroecology transition

(20) On a scale from 1 to 5 to which extent do national policies aim to support the following principles and practices associated with agroecology transition?

	(1) To a high extent	(2) To some extent	(3) Neutral	(4) To a limited extent	(5) Not at all	(x) I don't know
Integrated Pest Management and Biological Control						
Conservation Tillage						
Mixed Cropping Systems						
Diversified Crop Rotation						
Cover Crops						
Fertiliser and Nutrient Management Efficiency						
Biodiversity Preservation						
Circularity in Biomass Utilisation						
Wetland Restoration/Paludiculture						
Sustainable Water Management						
Multi-stakeholder innovation arrangements such as living labs						
Other co-creation arrangements in agriculture (e. g communities of practice, farmer field schools etc)						

(21) If other, please specify

(22) Which specific policies are the most relevant for the transition towards agroecology in your country - and why?

(23) What are the most important limitations in national and European policies with respect to agroecology in your country?

(24) Other reflections regarding policies supporting an agroecology transition?

3.8. Opportunities for advancing agroecology-based practices

(25) On a scale from 1 to 5, to which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding opportunities for a transition towards agroecology-based practices and research infrastructures?

	(1) Fully agree	(2) Agree	(3) Neutral	(4) Partly agree	(5) Disagree	(x) I don't know
Current national policies sufficiently foster agroecology transition						
Current European policies sufficiently foster agroecology transition						
Resource allocations are sufficient to support agroecology transition						
Advisory systems sufficiently foster agroecology transition						
A transition towards agroecology-based practices is seen as a societal concern in my country						
The current organization of the food market supports agroecological initiatives						
The underlying values of the current agriculture and food production system sufficiently foster an agroecology transition						

(26) What are the most important barriers for an agroecology transition in the country, and why are these barriers seen as important?

(27) Other reflections regarding opportunities for advancing agroecology-based production methods?

3.9. Best practice examples of agroecology initiatives

For the forthcoming partnership we need to showcase best practice cases of agroecology living labs and research infrastructure in Europe. Therefore, we kindly ask you to provide information about relevant initiatives within your country. We will use this list as an entry point for further inquiry with the enlisted contact person, therefore, please provide updated contact data.

Please bear in mind that we need as many initiatives as possible, therefore, please provide an overview of as many initiatives as possible. If you need more entries, please copy/paste the table below.

Agroecology initiative #1

Entry	Reply
Name of agroecology initiative:	
When was the initiative initiated?	
Scale of operation (Local/Regional/National/International) :	
Scope of initiative (primary production, value chain or what is the focus of the initiative) (briefly <100 words)	
Which user groups are involved? (Farmers and/or farmer associations, policy makers, researchers, value chain actors, consumers, other)	
How are user groups involved (in living labs, communities of practices, farmer fields schools etc.)	
Additional information (optional)	
Name of contact person :	
Contact detail (Email) :	

Agroecology initiative #2

Entry	Reply
Name of agroecology initiative:	
When was the initiative initiated?	

Scale of operation (Local/Regional/National/International) :	
Scope of initiative (primary production, value chain or what is the focus of the initiative) (briefly <100 words)	
Which user groups are involved? (farmers and/or farmer associations, policy makers, researchers, value chain actors, consumers, other)	
How are user groups involved (in living labs, communities of practices, farmer fields schools etc.)	
Additional information (optional)	
Name of contact person :	
Contact detail (Email) :	

Agroecology initiative #3

Entry	Reply
Name of agroecology initiative:	
When was the initiative initiated?	
Scale of operation (Local/Regional/National/International) :	
Scope of initiative (primary production, value chain or what is the focus of the initiative) (briefly <100 words)	
Which user groups are involved? (Farmers and/or farmer associations, policy makers, researchers, value chain actors, consumers, other)	
How are user groups involved (in living labs, communities of practices, farmer fields schools etc.)	
Additional information (optional)	
Name of contact person :	
Contact detail (Email) :	

(Please copy/paste more if needed)

3.10. Ending

28. Other messages or reflections of relevance for the themes of the survey and for the future partnership on agroecology?

4. Reporting template

When you have completed the round of interviews with the NCPs, please provide a short national report summarising the key findings of the interviews in the format given below. For each chapter, please write a small section (circa 500 words) summarising points raised in the interviews. In your text please consider and report when there are divergence across the informants as well as internal variation within the countries.

Additionally, please report all data from the closed questions in the template at the end of the list.

Please bear in mind that these sections will appear as appendices to the deliverables, therefore, please note that the text will be published fully or in parts. The report will be used to complete several deliverables, thus please avoid cross references to other chapters in the national report as they may be used in separate deliverables.

Section overview

1) Background information of the National Contact Points

- Here briefly clarify which participants were used as informants in the interviews?

2) Definitions of agroecology

- Here please elaborate how agroecology is interpreted and implemented in the country and whether there are different understandings of agroecology in use across the country.

3) The extent of agroecology-based practices

- Here please elaborate on the use of agroecology based practices in the country, which practices and principles are most common, which are less used and

4) Research and innovation systems in support of agroecology

- Here please elaborate on state of the research and innovation system in the country with respect to agroecology, including challenges and need for improvement.

5) Competencies for an agroecology transition

- Here please elaborate on the competencies available within the country with respect to agroecology.

6) Involvement of stakeholders in the agroecology transition

- Here please elaborate on stakeholders structure and organization within the country, including their alignment with agroecology.

7) Policies in support of agroecology

- Here please elaborate how agroecology is reflected in existing policies and which policies are most relevant with respect to agroecology transition.

8) Opportunities for advancing agroecology-based practices

- Here please elaborate stakeholder’s reflections regarding the opportunities for advancing an agroecology transition within the country.

9) Best practice examples of agroecology living labs

- Please copy/paste all the table entries you have completed during your interviews with national contact points providing a full list of different and relevant initiatives in the country. Please bear in mind that it is important for the forthcoming partnership that we identify as many relevant initiatives as possible.

10) Additional reflections

- Open entry that allows you to present relevant aspects that have appeared during your inquiry or additional points raised by interviewees.

Template for the reporting of closed questions

The template should be attached the national report as appendix. Here, please note the value of the assessment provided by the interviewee (1-5) and note “x” for “I don’t know”.

	Interviewee #1	Interviewee #2	Interviewee #3	Interviewee #4	Interviewee #5	Please insert more rows if needed
Question #2 (Which of the following stakeholder categories do you belong to?) (note with “x”)						
Public administration						
Researcher/Scientist						
NGO (please specify)						
Question #3 (On a scale from 1-5 how important are the different dimensions of agroecology in your country?)						
Practices						
Science						
Social Movements						

Question #5 (On a scale from 1 to 5 how commonly applied are the following agroecological principles and/or agroecology-based practices in your country?)						
Integrated Pest Management and Biological Control						
Conservation Tillage						
Mixed Cropping Systems						
Diversified Crop Rotation						
Cover Crops						
Fertiliser and Nutrient Management Efficiency/recycling						
Biodiversity Preservation						
Circularity in Biomass Utilisation						
Wetland Restoration with Paludiculture						
Sustainable Water Management						
Other						
Question #9 (On a scale from 1 to 5 to which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding research and innovation systems in support of agroecology in your country?)						
Research infrastructures (research facilities) are sufficiently attuned to support agroecology transition						
Research programs have focus on agroecology transition						
Sufficient financial resources are allocated for research into agroecology-based practices						
Farmers needs in an agroecology transition are sufficiently reflected in current research activities						
Living labs and other forms of multi-actor involvement are used in agroecological research and innovation						
On farm experimentation is often applied in research activities						
Question #13 (On a scale from 1 to five, how would you classify the state of the following elements in the context of agroecology in your country?)						
Education of farmers in agricultural colleges						
Technological infrastructure in the farming sector						
Knowledge networks among farmers						
Farm advisory service						
Resources available for training/retraining of farmers						
Farmer networks for knowledge sharing						

Other						
Question #16 (On a scale from 1 to (4) five to which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding stakeholder involvement with respect to agroecology related matters in your country?)						
Stakeholders are organised in associations that represent their interests						
Stakeholder associations possess a high level of technical expertise						
Stakeholders' views are taken into consideration in policymaking						
Stakeholders are well integrated in research programmes						
Stakeholder associations representing farmers have a strong interest in pursuing an agroecology transition						
Living labs and other open innovation arrangements are frequently used in to foster transition within your country						
Stakeholders are actively participating in multi-stakeholder living labs						
Question #20 (On a scale from 1 to 5 to which extent do national policies aim to support the following principles and practices associated with agroecology transition?)						
Integrated Pest Management and Biological Control						
Conservation Tillage						
Mixed Cropping Systems						
Diversified Crop Rotation						
Cover Crops						
Fertiliser and Nutrient Management Efficiency						
Biodiversity Preservation						
Circularity in Biomass Utilisation						
Wetland Restoration/Paludiculture						
Sustainable Water Management						
Multi-stakeholder innovation arrangements such as living labs						
Other co-creation arrangements in agriculture (e. g. communities of practice, farmer field schools etc)						
Question #25 (On a scale from 1 to 5, to which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding opportunities for a transition towards agroecology-based practices and research infrastructures?)						

Current national policies sufficiently foster agroecology transition						
Current European policies sufficiently foster agroecology transition						
Resource allocations are sufficient to support agroecology transition						
Advisory systems sufficiently foster agroecology transition						
A transition towards agroecology-based practices is seen as a societal concern in my country						
The current organization of the food market supports agroecological initiatives						
The underlying values of the current agriculture and food production system sufficiently foster an agroecology transition						

Appendix A : Information letter for collecting research data

Information letter

Collection of data for research

Name and organisation of data collector: (to be filled in by research team)

Name of the research participant: _____

I,; _____ (the research participant), have been informed that:

1. Data is being collected as part of the project ALL-Ready.
2. Data will be used for scientific analysis, publication and dissemination activities.
3. Data will be anonymized for publication/dissemination purposes.
4. Data will be analysed by members of the ALL-Ready project.
5. Participation is voluntary.
6. Consent for participation in the project can be withdrawn at any time by contacting the data collector.

Signature: _____ (participant)

Signature: _____ (data collector)

Date _____

Article 13 - EU GDPR: "Information to be provided where personal data are collected from the data subject"

1. Where personal data relating to a data subject are collected from the data subject, the controller shall, at the time when personal data are obtained, provide the data subject with all of the following information:

- (a) the identity and the contact details of the controller and, where applicable, of the controller's representative;
- (b) the contact details of the data protection officer, where applicable; *Please contact Aarhus University at dpo@au.dk*
- (c) the purposes of the processing for which the personal data are intended as well as the legal basis for the processing;

(d) where the processing is based on point (f) of [Article 6\(1\)](#), the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party;

(e) the recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data, if any;

(f) where applicable, the fact that the controller intends to transfer personal data to a third country or international organization and the existence or absence of an adequacy decision by the Commission, or in the case of transfers referred to in [Article 46](#) or [47](#), or the second subparagraph of [Article 49\(1\)](#), reference to the appropriate or suitable safeguards and the means by which to obtain a copy of them or where they have been made available.

2. In addition to the information referred to in paragraph 1, the controller shall, at the time when personal data are obtained, provide the data subject with the following further information necessary to ensure fair and transparent processing:

(a) the period for which the personal data will be stored, or if that is not possible, the criteria used to determine that period;

(b) the existence of the right to request from the controller access to and rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing concerning the data subject or to object to processing as well as the right to data portability;

(c) where the processing is based on point (a) of [Article 6\(1\)](#) or point (a) of [Article 9\(2\)](#), the existence of the right to withdraw consent at any time, without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal;

(d) the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority;

(e) whether the provision of personal data is a statutory or contractual requirement, or a requirement necessary to enter into a contract, as well as whether the data subject is obliged to provide the personal data and of the possible consequences of failure to provide such data;

(f) the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, referred to in [Article 22\(1\)](#) and (4) and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.

3. Where the controller intends to further process the personal data for a purpose other than that for which the personal data were collected, the controller shall provide the data subject prior to that further processing with information on that other purpose and with any relevant further information as referred to in paragraph 2.

4. Paragraphs 1, 2 and 3 shall not apply where and insofar as the data subject already has the information.

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